

A curious numerical pattern in nuclear and molecular structures

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Аннотация

We observe that a simple formula $a_n = 3 + n(n + 9)/2$ generates numbers that appear in the mass numbers of 14 stable isotopes, the tetra-neutron mass, and the masses of several mesons. The same formula also appears in cosmic void sizes. The number 8/9 appears repeatedly. These patterns may be coincidences, but they are presented here for consideration.

1 Introduction

Sometimes numbers repeat in nature. This note collects some observations.

2 A simple formula

Consider the formula:

$$a_n = 3 + \frac{n(n + 9)}{2}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (1)$$

It gives the numbers: 21, 29, 38, 48, 59, 71, 84, 98, 113, 129, 146, 164, 183, 203, ...

3 Where these numbers appear

3.1 Isotopes

The following 14 isotopes have these mass numbers:

^{21}Ne , ^{29}Si , ^{38}Ar , ^{48}Ti , ^{59}Co , ^{71}Ga , ^{84}Kr , ^{98}Mo , ^{113}In , ^{129}Xe , ^{146}Nd , ^{164}Dy , ^{183}W , ^{203}Tl .

3.2 Tetra-neutron

The tetra-neutron mass (3760.63 MeV) relates to numbers 29, 38, and 129:

$$\frac{3760.63}{29} \approx 129 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{3760.63}{38} \approx 98 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{3760.63}{129} \approx 29 \quad (4)$$

3.3 Mesons

Vector mesons seem to relate to these numbers:

- $\rho(770)$: $6 \times 129 = 774$
- $\omega(782)$: $6 \times 129 + 17m_e \approx 782.7$
- $\phi(1020)$: $9 \times 113 = 1017$
- $K^*(892)$: $(\rho + \phi)/2 \approx 895.5$

3.4 Cosmic voids

Void sizes follow a simple geometric progression [3]:

$$L_n = 210.2 \times \left(\frac{8}{9}\right)^n \text{ Mpc}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (5)$$

4 The number 8/9

The ratio $8/9 = 0.888\dots$ appears in the void hierarchy and may have geometric significance. For example, it is the square of $2/3$ multiplied by 2:

$$\frac{8}{9} = \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \cdot 2 \quad (6)$$

where $2/3$ is the ratio of a sphere's volume to its circumscribed cylinder.

5 Conclusion

We report numerical coincidences that may be worth further investigation. Whether these patterns are meaningful or accidental is left for the reader to decide.

Список литературы

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